

STUDY OF THE PROCESS OF PROCESSING ZEOLITE WASTE INTO ALUMINUM OXIDE

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Abstract. *This article presents the results of a study of the processing of zeolite-containing waste generated at Shurtan Gas Chemical Complex LLC in order to obtain aluminum oxide. The chemical and mineral composition of the adsorbents KA-3A°, NaA-4A° and NaX (13X)-10A° was analyzed. The main attention was paid to studying the effect of temperature, processing time and sulfuric acid concentration on the extraction of aluminum oxide. It was found that the optimal processing conditions for different zeolite adsorbents differ. A scheme for the complex processing of zeolite-containing adsorbents using the acid method was developed. Recommendations for cleaning the resulting solutions from silica impurities and iron compounds are given.*

Keywords: *zeolites, aluminum oxide, sulfuric acid, acid processing, chemical composition, mineral composition, solution purification.*

Introduction. Zeolites are crystalline aluminosilicates with unique adsorption, catalytic and ion exchange properties, which makes them indispensable materials in many industrial processes [1]. Natural and synthetic zeolites are used due to their high porosity, large specific surface area, and ability to selectively adsorb molecules based on their size, shape, and polarity. Zeolites have a three-dimensional structure consisting of aluminosilicate tetrahedrons linked through oxygen bridges, creating regular pores and channels. These characteristics make zeolites excellent adsorbents and molecular sieves, particularly effective for gas separation processes, ion exchange, and catalysts in the petrochemical industry [2].

However, despite their widespread use and high efficiency, the use of zeolites is accompanied by the formation of a significant amount of waste. Zeolite waste, as a rule, includes spent sorbents and catalysts that have lost their activity or ability to adsorb as a result of contamination or structural changes. The problem of recycling this waste is becoming increasingly important due to its volumes and potential negative impact on the environment [3].

One of the promising areas of zeolite waste processing is the production of aluminum oxide, a valuable product used in various industries, including the production of ceramics, catalysts, abrasives, and electronics. Aluminum oxide (Al₂O₃) has high thermal stability, chemical inertness, and excellent mechanical properties, which makes it attractive for use in high-temperature and aggressive environments. The purpose of this study is to analyze and compare various methods of zeolite waste processing in order to obtain high-purity aluminum oxide. This paper considers the main approaches to processing, including thermal, chemical, and combined processing. In addition, their efficiency, economic feasibility, and environmental aspects are assessed. Thus, the study of zeolite waste processing into aluminum oxide is an important area of both scientific and practical significance. The development of effective waste disposal methods

contributes to the rational use of natural resources, a reduction in anthropogenic load on the environment, and the creation of closed technological cycles [4-6].

Methods of chemical analysis

The raw materials, semi-finished products and finished products were analyzed for the content of aluminum, sodium chloride, potassium, calcium, magnesium, sulfates, water-insoluble residue and moisture. Calcium and magnesium were determined by the complexometric method [7]. The method is based on the change in the color of the indicator (fluorexone when determining calcium and acid chromium dark blue when determining magnesium) during the interaction of calcium and magnesium ions with trilon B.

Sulfates were determined by the gravimetric method [8]. The method is based on the precipitation of sulfates with barium chloride in an acidic medium and subsequent weighing of the precipitate. The mass fraction of chlorine ion was determined using the mercurimetric method by titrating chlorides with a solution of mercury nitrate in the presence of the indicator diphenylcarbazone [9].

Water in solid samples was determined by drying in a drying oven to constant weight at a temperature of 100-105 °C. The density of solutions and pulps was determined using a pycnometer PZh-2 according to. The kinematic viscosity of solutions and pulps was measured using glass capillary viscometers VPZh-1 and VPZh-2 [10].

Identification of solid phases was carried out using chemical, X-ray phase and infrared spectroscopic methods. X-ray phase analysis was performed on a Dron-3.0 diffractometer with filtered copper radiation at a voltage of 40 kV, a current of 20 MA, and a counter disk speed of 2 deg/min.

Results and discussion. The chemical and mineral compositions of zeolite-containing waste from *Shurtan Gas and Chemical Complex LLC* are presented in Tables 1 and 2. The average content of Al₂O₃ in adsorbents is KA-3A° - 13.61, NaA-4A° -10.57, NaX (13 X)-10A° - 12.21%.

Table 1. Chemical composition of zeolite-containing adsorbents used in Shurtan Gas Chemical Complex LLC

C omponents	Zeolites, average content of components, %		
	KA-3A°	NaX (13X)-10 A°	NaA-4A°
SiO ₂	62.90	65,62	68.50
P ₂ O ₅	0.08	0.004	0.08
Al ₂ O ₃	13.61	12.21	10.57
TiO ₂	0.34	0.07	0.18
Fe ₂ O ₃	3.00	1.25	0.68
FeO	0.14	0.06	0.07
CaO	0.61	2.07	2.52
MgO	1.51	0.64	0.88
Na ₂ O	1.36	1.90	0.24
K ₂ O	4.04	4.14	3.12
S _{gen}	0.007	0.016	<0.05
MnO	0.11	0.14	0.03
H ₂ O	3.88	3.82	5.10

P .p .p	9.16	8.22	7.70
Sum	100.75	100.16	99.67

Table 2. Mineral composition of zeolite-containing materials used in Shurtan Gas Chemical Complex LLC

Mineral	Zeolites, content of mineral phases , %		
	KA-3A°	NaX (13X)-10 A °	NaA-4A°
Clinoptilolite	45–65	60–66	63–74
Mordenite	-	-	7
Montmorillonite	15–20	3–5	3–5
Hydromicas	3–5	-	-
Quartz	3–10	3–5	1–3
Calcite	2–5	-	-
Microcline	3–5	3–5	-
Cristobalite	2–3	10–12	15–18
X-ray amorphous phase	<5	10–12	<10

The efficiency of alumina extraction was studied under the following acid treatment conditions: temperature, treatment duration and acid concentration.

Fig. 1 shows the alumina extraction curves depending on the temperature in the range from 20 to 98 °C at a sulfuric acid concentration of 50-70%.

Fig. 1. Dependence of Al₂O₃ extraction by sulfuric acid on temperature (zeolite-containing adsorbents: W)–KA-3A°:X-NaX (13 X)-10A°: B- NaA-4A°)

At n. u . extraction Al₂O₃ varies from 23 to 33%. Almost complete extraction (96%) of alumina from the NaA-4A° adsorbent occurs at 60 °C, while 80 °C is required for the KA-3A° adsorbent. Further increase in temperature has virtually no effect on the efficiency of aluminum oxide extraction. The most difficult to extract alumina was from the NaX (13X)-10A° adsorbent–82% at 98 °C.

The data on the extraction of Al₂O₃ depending on the duration of acid treatment of zeolite wastes in the time interval from 20 to 120 minutes at 70 °C were obtained (Fig. 2). Almost 97% of alumina from the adsorbent NaX (13 X)-10A° and the adsorbent KA-3A° passes into solution within 60 and 80 minutes, respectively.

Fig. 2. Dependence of Al₂O₃ extraction by sulfuric acid on the duration of processing (zeolite-containing adsorbents: W - KA-3A° : X - NaX (13 X)-10A°:B - NaA-4A°)

With increasing exposure time, the extraction increases by 1%. For the zeolite adsorbent NaA-4A°, a longer treatment is required: with 120 minutes of exposure, the extraction is 91%.

Figure 3 shows the curves of alumina extraction depending on the sulfuric acid concentration in the range from 20 to 90% at 70 °C and an exposure time of 100 min. About 98% of alumina from the KA-3A° adsorbent and the NaA-4A° adsorbent is extracted during treatment with 60 and 80% H₂SO₄, respectively. Treatment with 90% sulfuric acid does not affect the extraction. More than 90% of Al₂O₃ passes into solution from the NaX (13 X)-10A° adsorbent when exposed to 80% sulfuric acid.

Fig. 3. Dependence of the extraction of Al₂O₃ on the concentration of H₂SO₄ (zeolite-containing adsorbents: W - KA - 3A° ; X - NaX (13 X)-10A°; B - NaA- 4A°)

Schematically, the reaction of acid decomposition of zeolites can be represented as follows.

Reaction (1) occurs predominantly at high temperatures and acid concentrations.

An important point in the acid processing of zeolite waste is the different migration paths of the main components. Most of the alumina passes into solution, while silica remains in the sediment. It has been experimentally established that when exposed to acids, zeolite-containing waste decomposes to form aluminum salts in the form of.

When processing zeolite-containing waste with acids, 40-95% Fe₂O₃ and some amount of SiO₂ pass into the solution along with alumina. Therefore, it is necessary to purify the solution from impurities. One of the methods for separating aluminum and iron is to increase the concentration of sulfuric acid in the solution, which leads to the formation of an aluminum sulfate precipitate (Al₂(SO₄)₃). The precipitate can be separated by filtration, and the mother liquor containing iron compounds can be used to decompose a new portion of zeolite-containing waste. Another method of purification is the crystallization of aluminum sulfate from the solution as a

result of its evaporation. In the system $\text{Al}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 - \text{Fe}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 - \text{H}_2\text{O}$, double salts are not formed between iron sulfate and aluminum sulfate, which allows the separation of aluminum sulfate without iron sulfate, which will concentrate in the solution. Aluminum sulfate after the first crystallization does not meet the requirements for iron impurities due to the capture of the mother liquor. Therefore, after separation of the mother liquor, aluminum sulfate can be dissolved in hot water and the resulting solution cooled again to separate pure crystals.

In addition, the sorption method can be used to separate aluminum and iron sulfate compounds, for which ion exchangers of various types, cationites, anionites of various basicities, aminocarboxylic acids are used. amopholites and oxidized carbons. The depth of purification of acidic solutions depends on the initial amount of iron oxide in the solution, and the choice of method for purifying aluminum compounds from iron is determined by the processing of specific zeolite-containing waste.

Thus, as a result of treating zeolite-containing waste with sulfuric acid, it was established that the efficiency of Al_2O_3 extraction depends on the conditions of exposure (temperature, duration of treatment, acid concentration) and the composition of zeolite adsorbents (KA-3A°, NaX (13 X)-10A°, NaA-4A°). The optimal conditions for acid processing for zeolite-containing waste KA-3A° are: processing duration-80 min, sulfuric acid concentration - 60%, temperature - 80°C: adsorbent NaX (13 X)-10A°: duration - 60 min. acid concentration - 80%, temperature - 98 °C: NaA-4A° : duration - 120 min. acid concentration - 80%, temperature - 60 °C.

Conclusion. The conducted research has shown that the efficiency of aluminum oxide extraction from zeolite-containing waste of Shurtan Gas Chemical Complex LLC depends on the temperature, processing time and sulfuric acid concentration. For the KA-3A° adsorbent, the optimal conditions are: processing time - 80 minutes, sulfuric acid concentration-60%, temperature - 80 °C. For the NaX (13X)-10A° adsorbent: duration - 60 minutes, acid concentration - 80%, temperature - 98 °C. For the NaA-4A° adsorbent: duration - 120 minutes, acid concentration -80%, temperature - 60 °C. The developed scheme for the complex processing of zeolite-containing adsorbents allows achieving high efficiency of aluminum oxide extraction and minimizing the amount of by- products. Further research can be aimed at improving the proposed technology and adapting it to industrial conditions.

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